

QUESTIONS OF UNIQUE FEATURES OF ENTREPRENEURIAL LOGISTICS IN THE MARKETING SYSTEM

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Abstract: In the article, the specific features of business logistics in the marketing system are analyzed in detail, and aspects of the relationship between business logistics and marketing and management are highlighted.

Keywords: Macroeconomic stability, business environment, entrepreneurship, logistics, business logistics, marketing, management.

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In recent years, more than 15 laws aimed at increasing the role of private ownership and strengthening its protection, and further improving the business environment and business conditions, including «On the protection of private property and guarantees of the rights of owners», «On the guarantees of freedom of business activity», «Entrepreneurship «On the principles of licensing in the field of activity», «On family business», «On competition» laws were adopted. 186 types of licensing procedures and licenses, 65 statistical and 6 tax reporting forms were canceled.

The system of submission of tax and statistical reports, as well as the processes of registration of documents at the customs office, have been fully electronic.[1] As a result of the further development and liberalization of the economy in our country, a number of positive results have been achieved by the economic reforms. This is reflected, first of all, in the formation of a multi-level economy and the class of owners, in the provision of macroeconomic stability and on this basis, in the preparation of a solid ground for sustainable economic growth, in the creation of a favorable socio-economic environment for the development of private entrepreneurship, especially small business. In recent years, the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the life of society has been strengthened. In recent years, systematic measures aimed at increasing the level of use of the economic potential of small businesses are bearing fruit. Small business provides about 60% of the country's gross domestic product, one third of the volume of industrial products, 98% of agricultural products, and half of investments. At the same time, there are problems related to lending to small

businesses and private enterprises, providing them with material raw resources, and involving them in foreign economic activities. In particular, the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in filling the consumer market, ensuring the country's food independence, and forming real incomes of the population remains low.

In this regard, it is necessary to implement specific measures to increase the participation of small business and private entrepreneurship in solving the socio-economic tasks considered a priority for our country. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2016 «On additional measures to ensure the rapid development of business activity, comprehensive protection of private property and qualitative improvement of the business environment» was adopted, first of all, it is the basis for strengthening the legal protection of private property, creating favorable conditions for small business and private entrepreneurship and all-round support, increasing the share of this sector in the GDP, and solving the employment problem [2]. This requires the establishment of priorities for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the context of further liberalization of the economy, and the development of scientific and practical proposals and recommendations for solving existing problems in this field.

The current stage of economic reforms implemented in our country is characterized by the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. As a result of the implemented reforms, the field of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan is rapidly developing. After all, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is one of the most important priorities of the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan. Every activity in a favorable business environment encourages commercialization and competition. Correspondingly, the consumer has the opportunity to choose the most suitable product for purchase and consumption from the market. It is also clear that the priority of the consumer in free choice is equaled only by the entrepreneurial ability of the producer or seller, as a result of which entrepreneurship becomes a condition and symptom of viability for all participants of the market, not for some. The essence of entrepreneurial activity is the dependence and adaptation of the entrepreneur to the consumer, not the consumer to the entrepreneur. In fact, this idea is emphasized by F. Kotler as one of the 9 rules of modern marketing success [3].

In our opinion, in order to achieve the competitiveness of our national business in the domestic and foreign markets, it is very important to learn the accumulated experience and scientific conclusions on the fight for buyers in developed countries, and in this regard, they are undoubtedly useful.

Due to this economic situation, that is, due to the trends of time and value weight redistribution in economic processes, it was realized that it is necessary to abandon narrow interests and fierce competitive relations in approaches to the activities of functional departments (such as supply, storage, sales) and independent entities in large companies. Because the interest of only some of them in satisfying the needs of the consumer has warned the continuity of economic processes. After all, the fact that suppliers increased supply to eliminate the risk of shortage of raw materials led to a slowdown in the movement of financial funds. Using cheap packaging methods has not always been convenient for transporters. All of the above conditions made it necessary to take into account the movement of material resources in supply, preparation, storage and transportation of production stocks as a single flow in order to ensure a stable market balance. As a result, the science of logistics was created, which includes new methods and tools that ensure the mutual balance and compatibility of interests in the «supply-production-sale» processes. In fact, the dictionary meaning of «logistics» in ancient Greek (lodoz, gistos, logistca) meant «the art of calculation» and «observation». At the same time, it cannot be said that «logic» and «logistics» mean the same thing. The first means the causal relationship, the second means the organization of management in this relationship [4].

In this way, the foundation of a new scientific direction of entrepreneurship development was laid. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the Venn diagram to study the interrelationship and characteristics of business activities, logistics, and business logistics (Figure 1).

As a research object of logistics, the integrated flow process of supply, production, sale, which consists of various elements and aspects oriented to the goal, is defined.

According to the standards of economic development in the West, it took almost half a century for «logistics» to separate from «marketing» and «management» and receive a separate scientific direction. In Uzbekistan, during the historically short past years of independence - twenty-five years, the methods and means of «logistics» were seriously started to be used. For example, due to the abolition of the administrative management system, the restrictions on the benefits and guarantees of enterprises based on obligation, the abandonment of the «cost plus» price policy familiar to the market, and the end of the day of encouraging irresponsibility and fraud were the organizational basis of this process. Therefore, the above-mentioned evolutionary process creates an opportunity to understand the aspects necessary for the development of entrepreneurship in our national enterprises.

Entrepreneurship

1. Initiative;
2. Personal responsibility;
3. Private interest;
4. Ability to adapt to difficult situations;
5. Ability to imagine efficiency.

Business logistics:

1. Stock flow
rational organization;
2. Cost minimization;
3. Save time;
4. Achieving maximum benefit from the flow of available resources

Logistics

1. Total uninterrupted flow of reserves and processes; / 2. Exact time for current processes;
3. Reliance on market forces; / .
4. Synergistic efficiency

Figure 1. Distinctive features of business logistics

Abroad, market relations are known to have been perfected over the centuries to curb the «indolence» and social orientation. For our national entrepreneurship, the lack of such an opportunity requires that scientific directions such as «marketing», «management» and «logistics» be applied in accordance with the characteristics of the national market. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the approach shown in Fig. 2 to the interdependence of the concepts of «entrepreneurship», «logistics», «business logistics», «management» and «marketing».

Management:

1. Harmonization of interests;
2. To join forces;
3. Improving skills;
4. Increasing labor productivity

Business logistics

1. Priority of current approach;
2. Consumer of current processes
coordination with character;
3. Follow the rules of ACCURACY;
4. A combination of centralized management and free enterprise

Marketing:

1. What? For whom? In what way?
2. Influencing consumer choice;

3. Compliance with the 4R rule in the market;

4. Production of products for sale

Figure 2. Business logistics with management and marketing Relatedness

As the figure shows, business logistics is an important complementary tool in ensuring the practicality of principles in management and marketing strategies. According to the analyzes of Western representatives, managing the movement of material goods as a single flow accelerates the circulation of working capital; leads to savings of material reserves up to 30-50%, reduces the time of delivery of material goods from the initial source to the final consumer by 25-45% [4]. International experience shows that the effective use of logistics methods and tools depends, first of all, on the business environment. In the conditions of economic liberalization, the interrelationship of the business environment with logistics in our country is expressed by several factors. On the one hand, the successful implementation of logistics depends on scientific research areas such as marketing and management, and on the other hand, it comes from the comfort level of internal and external factors in the business environment (Figure 3).

The following organizational and institutional conditions play an important role in the improvement of the business environment:

- regulatory documents;
- political situation;
- state intervention;
- national mentality.

Also, the business environment is explained by external and internal factors. Legal protection, support and encouragement of the entrepreneur are taken into account as external factors. Internal factors are:

- material and moral potential of the entrepreneur;
- awareness of the economic situation;

- covers such things as adherence to commonality of interests and responsibilities and application of experience, competence and skills.

Figure 3. Interrelationship of business environment and logistics

Most of our national researchers have made significant advances in the field of studying, analyzing, objectively evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of the business environment in transition and making effective decisions and implementing them.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to emphasize the following main points in these studies:

1. Due to the priority of inductive approaches in entrepreneurship research, the high importance of the development of certain sectors and industries;
2. Proposals for deepening regulatory-legal, organizational-economic reforms should be given a leading place in research conclusions;
3. The need to improve practical skills and skills in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship research;

The need to supplement the three factors of reproduction (labor, capital, natural resources) with the fourth - entrepreneurship ability, and to strengthen the position of the decisive factor of entrepreneurship ability, which is a simple structural element, etc.

In conclusion, we can say that marketing logistics is a set of theoretical and practical rules related to the optimization processes of information, material and service flows that follow the enterprise's marketing activities in the market. Marketing logistics is based on processes: customer relationship management, supplier relationship management, distributor relationship management, competitor relationship management.

Implementation of the concept of marketing logistics using modern business concepts provides a qualitatively new level of wholesale and retail development. Because at present, it is very difficult to achieve a competitive advantage only by forming a product, price and communication strategy.

Currently, competition is growing not between individual goods, but between their distribution channels. Therefore, marketing logistics makes it possible to develop a distribution channel strategy, ensure the competitiveness of distribution channels, and gain stable competitive advantages in the trade marketing system.

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